

nated to metal(II) ion, and the Dq values indicate that the ligand field around the metal is sufficiently strong. The values of Racah parameters calculated for some complexes further suggest a considerable degree of covalency or orbital overlap in the complexes^{11,12}.

References

1. I. GAMO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1961, **34**, 760.
2. M. M. PATEL and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1046.
3. I. GAMO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1961, **34**, 760.
4. G. SARTORI, C. FURLANI and A. DAMIENI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **8**, 119.
5. L. W. DALCH and U. E. HANWYAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **72**, 8673.
6. P. TRYSSI and J. J. CHARETTE, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1967, **19**, 1407.
7. M. N. SAHA and B. M. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 10.
8. S. SATPATHY and B. SAHU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 188.
9. J. MICHAEL and R. A. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 71.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, S. M. NELSON and T. M. SHEPPARD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **6**, 810.
11. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1966, p. 221, 223.
12. S. K. MADAN and D. I. MUELLER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 177.

Complexes of Sulphamethizole with Copper and Silver

(Miss) SHARDA GARG, V. S. PATEL and S. S. GUPTA

Chemical Laboratories, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal

Manuscript received 21 January 1982, accepted
12 November 1982

TRANSITIONAL metals like Fe, Co, Ag, Au, Cu have long been used in medicines. Kaushal and coworkers^{1,2} have prepared a large number of metal sulphonamide complexes, some of which are found to be more potent than the parent sulphonamides. Keeping this in view, complexes of sulphamethizole (I) with cupric chloride and silver nitrate were prepared by us.

Experimental

Composition of the complex: Standard solutions of cupric chloride (0.02 M), silver nitrate (0.02 M) and sulphamethizole (0.01 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure ethanol. 10 ml of the ligand was diluted to 50 ml and titrated against the metal salt solutions using 'Tosniwal' conductivity

bridge and dip type electrodes at 28°. The results after volume corrections indicate 2 : 1 sulphamethizole cupric chloride complex and 1 : 1 sulphamethizole silver nitrate complex, respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The nature of the copper complex was also studied spectrophotometrically using Vasburgh and Cooper³ method. For this, mixtures containing 2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 proportions of equimolecular solutions of sulphamethizole and cupric chloride (0.04 M) in spectroscopically pure ethanol were taken and the absorbances measured. The results indicated that only one complex with 2 : 1 ratio is formed. Formation of 2 : 1 complex was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation⁴ using absorbance as the index property (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

Isolation and analysis:

Sulphamethizole-cupric chloride complex: Sulphamethizole (2.5 g) and cupric chloride (0.8 g) in 2 : 1 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A dark green solution was

obtained which on refluxing over water bath for 45 min gave a dark green complex. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield 3.05 g, m.p. 170°.

Sulphamethizole-silver nitrate complex : Sulphamethizole (2.5 g) and silver nitrate (1.57 g) in 1 : 1 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring when a thick white precipitate formed. On refluxing over water bath for 1 hr, a white crystalline complex was obtained. It was cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield 2.58 g, m.p. 228°.

Analytical results of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. Nitrogen was estimated by modified Kjeldahl's method⁵. Sulphur by Messenger's method and metals by standard volumetric or gravimetric procedures.

TABLE 1

Composition of the complex	Analysis% ; Found(Calcd.)					
	Metal	Cl/NO ₃	C	H	N	S
(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂) ₂ .CuCl ₂	10.27 (9.28)	11.10 (10.48)	31.1 (32.05)	3.46 (2.98)	14.11 (16.61)	18.35 (19.07)
(C ₉ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂) ₂ .AgNO ₃	23.72 (24.52)	—	24.45 (24.57)	2.60 (2.29)	12.36 (12.73)	15.34 (14.57)

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titration results plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that sulphamethizole forms 2 : 1 complex with copper. Yamabe and coworkers⁶ have also reported 2 : 1 ratio for various copper-sulphadrag complexes. Similarly, sulphamethizole forms 1 : 1 complex with silver. Turner and coworkers⁷ have also suggested 1 : 1 complex of sulphadiazene with silver.

The sulphamethizole-copper complex has also been studied spectrophotometrically at two concentrations. Stability constant (log k) is calculated by Turner-Anderson method⁸ and found to be 4.82. The free energy change (ΔF) is -6.7 Kcal/mole. The analytical results correspond to the compositions (C₉H₁₀O₂N₄S₂)₂.CuCl₂ and C₉H₁₀O₂N₄S₂.AgNO₃, respectively. On the basis of above results following tentative structures, II and III, are assigned to the copper and silver complexes, respectively.

Structure II is supported by observations of Wang Kyn Leo⁹ who have given chelate structures to some of the sulphadrag complexes. Sulphamethizole-eupric chloride complex on boiling with water gives

test for chloride ion which confirms that chlorine is attached by primary valency to the complex, while sulphamethizole-silver nitrate complex also give test for nitrate ion.

Structures II and III are further supported by infrared spectral data. Metal-nitrogen frequencies were observed at 660 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes which are in agreement with the observations of Chaturvedi and Kaushal¹⁰. Similarly, metal-oxygen frequencies were observed at 690 ± 5 cm⁻¹. Two bands were observed near 3400 and 3300 cm⁻¹ of medium and strong intensity in the ligand with Cu and Ag complexes, indicating that anilino NH₂ group is not altered in any way. Gupta¹¹ has also suggested that p-NH₂ group of sulphadrag does not take part in coordination. A characteristic frequency at 1570 cm⁻¹ was observed in copper complex only which indicates the formation of six membered heterocyclic chelating ring. No such frequency was observed in ligand or in silver complex indicating that no chelation takes place in silver complex.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the Principal, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal for facilities, to C.D.R.I., Lucknow for estimations of C and H, and to Werner Hindustan Ltd., for the gift of a pure sample of sulphamethizole. One of them (S. G.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for a Junior Research Fellowship, while (S. S. G.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial support.

References

1. K. K. PANDEY and R. KAUSHAL, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 96.
2. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1135.
3. W. C. VASBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437 ; 1942, **64**, 1630.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **10**, 113 ; 1936, **10**, 97.
5. M. ASHRAF, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 559.
6. SHIGERU YAMABE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **56**, 10291f.
7. S. E. TURNER and MICHAEL, *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **83**, 171362z.
8. S. E. TURNER and R. C. ANDERSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 912.
9. WANG KYN LEO, *J. Pharm. Soc. Korea*, 1969, **13**, 97.
10. K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, private communication.
11. A. P. GUPTA, D. SHARMA and D. G. BANERJEA, *Sci. Cult.*, 1977, **43**, 181.